

Project title
Navigating Unconventional Childbirth in Lithuania: Choice, Risk, and Medical Perspectives on Home Birth and Elective C-Sections

Project promoters

Row No.	Full name	Unit
Main researcher		
1.	Ieva Bisigirskaitė	Faculty of Philology, Centre for Scandinavian Studies
Other promoters		
2.	Živilė Sabonytė-Balšaitienė	Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Clinical Medicine, Clinic of Obstetrics and Gynaecology
3.	Ugnė Gudžinskaitė	Faculty of Philosophy, Institute of Sociology and Social Work

Project description

1. Purpose and objectives

Facing gradual demographic decline, Lithuania has been emphasizing the improvement of conditions for families and mothers within its political discourse. However, Lithuanian maternal grass-root campaigns, particularly campaigns for legal home birth and caesarean delivery on maternal request, point to the existing gaps in reproductive healthcare access.

With the overall purpose of improving perinatal healthcare for Lithuanian women, especially those seeking unconventional birth options, this research will address access gaps, clarify women's reproductive attitudes and realities, and incorporate the insights of perinatal health professionals, providing critical knowledge to guide policymakers and healthcare practitioners in meeting the needs of understudied groups.

This study combines a mixed-method inquiry into the motivations behind Lithuanian women's alternative childbirth choices as well as the attitudes of perinatal healthcare practitioners towards these practices. While these birth practices are often simplistically portrayed as belonging to opposite sides on the "medical" versus "natural" spectrum within discursive constructions embedded in so-called "birth wars", we see them as potentially offering a nuanced complimentary perspective on the reproductive realities of Lithuanian women.

To accomplish these objectives, our study involves conducting an interdisciplinary mixed method study rooted in the epistemologies of critical medical humanities. More precisely, given the interdisciplinary nature of the research team, we aim to 1) determine the motivations behind Lithuanian women's choices of planned unassisted home births and caesarean deliveries and, thus, fill the knowledge gap surrounding unconventional birth practices by providing qualitatively grounded insights. Additionally, we aim to 2) provide quantitatively grounded insights in order to determine the prevalence of these choices and define the demographic profiles of women who choose them. Additionally, we aim to 3) conduct qualitative research on the attitudes, beliefs, and experiences of perinatal healthcare practitioners (including OB-GYNs and midwives) regarding planned unassisted home births and elective caesarean deliveries, thereby identifying potential areas of conflict or alignment with women's choices and 4) furnish more specific

recommendations for women's health institutions, potentially prompting a reassessment of existing protocols and facilitating models of individualised medicine for perinatal care.

2. The relevance and innovativeness of the scientific idea

Recently, there has been some notable interest in women's experiences and expectations of birth in Lithuania both by academic scholars and NGOs. However, despite considerable public and media attention, experiences or motivations of women who have birthed/would prefer to birth at home or by C-section on maternal request have so far been mostly understudied and no study has offered a comparative approach. Moreover, there is a lack of quantitative data regarding how many women choose these delivery methods in Lithuania. Additionally, besides analysis of dominant discourses within the Lithuanian media and a few minor studies, the attitudes of perinatal healthcare practitioners (such as OB-GYNs and midwives) towards these practices remain unknown. However, even with limited research, it's clear that interpersonal care significantly shapes Lithuanian women's *hospital* birth experiences. Additionally, specific demographic profiles and previous negative hospital birth experiences are more common among women who choose unconventional birth methods and exhibit a "reflexive patient" mentality, marked by active informed decision-making.

Internationally, while inquiries into the motives behind home delivery or C-section on maternal request exist, only a few offer a comparative approach to alternative birth choices. Even less is done in trying to incorporate attitudes to alternative birth choices both from the perspective of birthing individuals and clinicians, particularly from the perspective using a mixed-method approach. However, the prevailing market-based model of maternity care, which frames services as a transaction between "providers" and "consumers", is increasingly challenged by international researchers for its tendency to render maternity care providers and other crucial agents within the "birthing assemblage" invisible. This approach also fails to recognise that unconventional birth methods cause important challenges for women, their families and medical staff. Crucially, their role as essential agents in the dis/embodyed experience of birth, as revealed in women's narratives, underscores the importance of their inclusion in this research project. Additionally, the role of the social class is underlined in understanding women's attitudes towards birth experiences. And so is the split among the perinatal health practitioners themselves over they support (or lack thereof in relation to certain birthing practices)

Drawing on epistemologies of medical humanities, a field that uses interdisciplinary approaches to critically analyze the contexts, experiences, and conceptual frameworks of medicine and healthcare, this study will offer a comparative analysis of planned unassisted home births and elective C-sections in Lithuania, providing both quantitative and qualitative understanding of women's motives behind these birth choices. Building on previous research performed, among others, by the members of the research team, this study will employ a mixed-methods approach and, unlike previous studies, will integrate the perspectives of both the birthing women and perinatal healthcare practitioners, offering a more comprehensive inquiry into attitudes of the agents involved in the process of delivery.

This research will gather data using a mixed-methods design. Qualitative data, from in-depth semi-structured interviews with women and maternity care practitioners, will be analyzed using tools of narrative medicine. Quantitative data will be obtained from existing MGIS surveys (2019-2024) and a new online survey created by the research team for healthcare practitioners, and will be analyzed using appropriate statistical tools, including factor analysis from sociological perspective. Finally, the findings will be analysed integrating theoretical concepts of matrifocal perspectives of narrative medicine, "embodiment theory" and "assemblage theory"

3. Project contents and work plan

Project content:

- An analysis of the data obtained by an online survey constructed and carried out by an NGO “Motinystę globojančių iniciatyvų sąjunga” (funded by Active Citizens Fund) who has by now carried out 4 consecutive surveys since 2019 concerned with women’s perception of their birth experience. This poll of quantitative data will be used to analyse responses of women’s childbirth experiences, including the ones concerned with the two unconventional birth practices and comparing them in the context of other experiences, also considering the demographic profile of the women who opt for these options.
 - An anonymous questionnaire to healthcare practitioners working in the field of perinatal healthcare in relation to their attitudes towards these two forms of “unconventional birth” practices; This survey explores healthcare practitioners’ attitudes, beliefs, and experiences regarding planned unassisted home births and elective caesarean deliveries, focusing on perceived risks and professional perspectives.
 - 6 semi-structures in-depth interviews with women who have given birth/are planning a home-birth; 6 semi-structures in-depth interviews with women who have given birth/are planning a C-section birth;
 - 5 semi-structures in-depth interviews with OB-GYN; 5 semi-structures in-depth interviews with midwives;
 - An interdisciplinary analysis of collected data from the perspective of medical humanities.
- All data collection will be conducted following ethical guidelines.

Project Plan

2025: May – December

Ieva Bisigirskaitė (I.B.) and Živilė Sabonytė-Balšaitienė (Ž.S.) prepare and submit an application to the Assessment of compliance with research ethics at the Faculty at Medicine;

All group members carry out an extensive literature review on alternative birth practices within the field of medical humanities, social policy, motherhood research (I.B.), within the field of medicine and medical humanities (Ž.S.), and within the field of social work, social policy and sociology of health Ugnė Gudžinskaitė (U.G.)

All group members work on creating an online survey for maternal care practitioners;

Ž.S. distributes information about the survey through her professional networks;

U.G. obtains qualitative data on alternative birth practices available from MGIS surveys re the demographic profile of the groups of women concerned and reasons and motivations behind unconventional birth;

U.G. prepares a research article for a high level international peer-reviewed journal based on her recently defended MA dissertation.

Ž.S. and I.B. forming a database of study participants for in-depth semi-structured interviews through personal and professional networks

Ž.S. and I.B. carries out in-depth interviews with maternity care professionals (The interviews will be digitally recorded, then transcribed verbatim);

I.B. applies for a Erasmus+ program in order to carry out a fellowship visit to the Centre of Medical Humanities at University of Uppsala, Sweden.

U.G. submits her articles to the journal *Sociology of Health & Illness* or other similar journal in the field of health and social sciences.

2026 January – December

I.B. consults Vilnius University in preparation of Research data management plan

The data collected in the first year of the project is analysed using methods described: all three members are working on the analysis of the data collected during the interviews, writing a research article for an international academic journal (e.g. *BMJ Medical Humanities* or *Journal of Medical Humanities*).

All three members present research finding at the conference on women’s health in Lithuania

I.B. and U.G. are preparing an article for a wider public outreach (15min.lt; Lrt.lt);

Ž.S. and I.B. are working on recommendations for institutions and women's health professionals on the outcomes of the research project.

4. Future perspectives of further topic development, implementation of results, and applicability. Technological readiness level of the foreseen results

Planned results of this research project are: 1) an Open Access publication by U.G. based on her findings, analysing data from MGIS surveys concerned with women's experiences of hospital birth will be published in an international peer-reviewed journal. 2) A scientific report will be presented at a conference organized by the Lithuanian Society of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists (LSOG) in 2026; 3. A scientific article will be submitted for publication in an international journal within the field of Medical Humanities (status: submitted by the end of the project). 4) A science popularization article will be published in Lithuanian media outlets such as www.15min.lt or www.lrt.lt; 5. An informal network will be developed with researchers at the Centre of Medical Humanities in Uppsala University, Sweden; 6. Recommendations for obstetrics and gynaecology medical professionals and institutions involved in women's reproductive health will be issued.

Future research will establish an international group to compare reproductive rights frameworks across Eastern Europe and the Baltics. Considering that Latvia has a more liberal package of services in the field of reproductive health, including free IVF treatment for single women, home-birth delivery centres, and access to C-section deliveries by maternal choice, a comparative study of medical professional attitudes towards alternative birth choices in Latvia and Lithuania, and potentially Sweden, will be pursued, with applications submitted to the Research Council of Lithuania. Moreover, this comparative approach will be expanded into understanding the scale and motivation behind "reproductive tourism" within the Baltic Sea region. Additionally, in case of successful networking experience with researchers at the Centre of Medical Humanities at the University of Uppsala, a comparative project would be developed including the Swedish context.

This current project lays the groundwork for future development through: 1) its expansion into a transdisciplinary and multicultural study of regional reproductive health, and 2) the introduction of posthumanist theoretical frameworks, which will be applied to analyze the politics of birth across multiple research contexts. A growing group of scholars interested in applications of posthumanist epistemologies and new materialism have underlined that anthropocentric analysis of "[M]aternal transition research [...] has reached conceptual saturation". Following this line of thinking, the future project would be based on the posthumanist conceptualisations of reproductive politics or reproductive tourism and would involve two or three contexts within the region (e.g. Lithuania, Latvia, Sweden). One of the potential funding bodies to apply for would be the Foundation of Baltic and East European Studies (Södertörn University, Sweden).

5. Indicate 5 of the most significant scientific publications that have been published by the members of the group in the last five years

Sabonytė-Balšaitienė, Živilė, Poškus, Tomas; Jasiūnas, Eugenijus; Ramašauskaitė, Diana; Bužinskienė, Diana; Drašutienė, Gražina Stanislava; Okulevičiūtė, Agnė; Zakarevičienė. "Risk Factors for Constipation During Pregnancy: A Multicentre Prospective Cohort Study." *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2024, art. 878, pp. 1-12. doi:10.1186/s12884-024-07098-3.

Sabonytė-Balšaitienė, Živilė, Poškus, Tomas; Jasiūnas, Eugenijus; Ramašauskaitė, Diana; Drašutienė, Gražina Stanislava. "Incidence and Risk Factors of Perianal Pathology During Pregnancy and Postpartum Period: A Prospective Cohort Study." *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, vol. 13, no. 8, 2024, art. 2371, pp. 1-16. doi:10.3390/jcm13082371.

Poškus, Tomas; **Sabonytė-Balšaitienė**, Živilė; Jakubauskienė, Lina; Jakubauskas, Matas; Stundienė, Ieva; Barkauskaitė, Gabija; Šmigelskaitė, Mantė; Jasiūnas, Eugenijus; Ramašauskaitė, Diana; Strupas, Kęstutis; Drąsutienė, Gražina Stanislava. “Preventing Hemorrhoids During Pregnancy: A Multicenter, Randomized Clinical Trial.” *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, vol. 22, no. 1, 2022, art. 374, pp. 1-7. doi:10.1186/s12884-022-04688-x.

Bužinskienė, Diana, **Živilė Sabonytė-Balšaitienė**, and Tomas Poškus. “Perianal Diseases in Pregnancy and After Childbirth: Frequency, Risk Factors, Impact on Women’s Quality of Life and Treatment Methods.” *Frontiers in Surgery*, vol. 9, 2022, art. 788823, pp. 1-5. doi:10.3389/fsurg.2022.788823.

Einikytė, Rūta, **Živilė Sabonytė-Balšaitienė**, Ingrida Pilypienė, Diana Ramašauskaitė, and Jelena Volochovič. “Naujagimių vėjaraupiai. Klinikinis atvejis ir literatūros apžvalga = Neonatal Varicella Zoster Virus Infection. Clinical Case and Literature Review.” *Lietuvos Akušerija ir Ginekologija*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2021, pp. 83-89. doi:10.37499/LAG.632.

Bisigirskaitė, I. “Mothers Challenging ‘unsafe’ Birth: A Matricentric Feminist Perspective on Maternal Activism in Lithuania”. *Journal of Mother Studies*, no. 9, Zenodo, Sept. 2024.

Bisigirskaitė, I. Choosing a Surname of Her Own: Non (Neo)-Traditional Femininities in Contemporary Lithuania. Diss. University of Zurich, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5167/uzh-205125>

Gudžinskaitė, U. “Moterų gimdymo praktikos ir patirtys Lietuvoje”. MA Diss. Vilniaus universitetas., 2022.

Mažulytė-Rašytinė, E., **Gudžinskaitė, U.**, Pukelienė, M. ”Moterų gimdymo patirtys Lietuvoje iki COVID-19 pandemijos ir jos laikotarpiu”, *Lietuvos akušerija ir ginekologija*. Kaunas : Vitae litera. ISSN 1392-5091. 2021, t. 24, Nr. 4, p. 308-316.

Mažulytė-Rašytinė, Eglė; **Gudžinskaitė, Ugnė.** ”The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on subjective childbirth experience and postpartum post-traumatic stress reactions in women who gave birth in Lithuania.” *European journal of psychotraumatology: Trauma and Mental Health during the Global Pandemic*: abstract book of the ESTSS 2021 virtual conference, vol. 12, no. S2. Taylor & Francis Ltd., 2021.

Funded research projects of I.B.

“Maternity in the Time of ‘Traditional Values’ and Femonationalism” co-applicant with Julia Gradska (PI) and Soheyla Yazdanpanah (Södertörn University, Sweden); January 2022 - December 2024; Funding scheme: The Foundation for Baltic and East European Studies; Position: Postdoctoral researcher

“New femininities in post-communist societies: refusing the name of the Mother” (working title of the doctoral project); August 2015 - August 2017; Funding scheme: Forschungskredit Candoc by The University of Zurich, Switzerland; Position: doctoral candidate (PI)

Project promoters: I.B. is a researcher in Gender, Culture and Motherhood studies, who has focused on questions of reproductive justice within media and political discourse due to her engagement in research on good-motherhood in nationalist constructions. Ž.S. is a practicing obstetrician-gynecologist, a lecturer and a researcher at Vilnius University. U.G. is a sociologist with a strong background in quantitative research methods and experience in working with an NGO specifically concerned with the quantitative data regarding women’s experiences in the maternal health sector in Lithuania.